

deviant. This is a visible phenomenon in a wide range of areas: from ticketless travel to the murder of a person. In a broad sense, a deviant is every person who deviates from the rules or goes astray. The main forms of deviant behavior include delinquency, criminality, alcoholism, drug addiction, prostitution, and suicide.

Now let's dwell on this issue itself, which we are considering.

Suicide is a vital problem that occurs in human life as much as it lives on earth. According to researchers, suicide is an anthropological phenomenon. Compared to the phenomenon of suicide in humans and animals, this action is distinguished by intelligence. The difference between animal suicide and people is that they fall into unconscious actions. Human suicide can be seen as an element of a new civilization. As we all know, when large tribal classes began to form, suicide performed a pragmatic social function, and it also contributed to the survival of single tribes. The first known suicides in the history of mankind are the deaths of children and the elderly during periods of famine in the first class structure. According to the course of history, the methods of suicide of people have changed and become more difficult. We all know that the voluntary parting of a person from life becomes more and more over the years.

Suicide is the death of a person by thinking. Suicide is an action that occurs in all cultures. Suicidal people are usually a group of people who have suffered from spiritual distress and are in a stressful state, unable to solve their problem. They often suffer from a mental illness, especially in a depressive state for a long time, and they despair of the future. Suicide is the leading cause of death worldwide, so it is considered one of the most pressing problems in society. According to many researchers, the official statistics of suicide underestimate its true number [3].

Is suicide a more insignificant phenomenon than a global geopolitical phenomenon? And when it comes to reality, it gives a certain assessment of what is happening in society and is a phenomenon that characterizes the real appearance of this society. At the same time, the existence of extensive and comprehensive statistical data of the subject of study of suicide entrusts Western sociologists with real success. Despite this, it is also important to remember the importance of studying suicide. After all, the social dimension of the number of suicides is characterized by constant stability and increasing from the dimension of total mortality, and therefore the first place in its study is given to the general indicators of suicide-as a response to the stagnation occurring in society. Each person perceives different situations that occur in society in their own way. In this work, I conduct only on objective facts and how they influenced Kazakh society, based on the collection of data of sociologists and their analysis.

First of all, it is necessary to give a definition of suicide. This term means "an act committed with the intention of depriving oneself of life", and in the scientific literature it is used in the sense that suicide is committed consciously, thoughtfully. Death, then, considers a situation committed by a person who is unable to respond to their actions or control them as an unhappy situation, and not a situation in which the unintentional result of the subject is a suicide. What is at the heart of this suicide phenomenon? A. G. Ambrumova and many researchers consider suicide as a concept as a phenomenon of socio-psychological maladaptation of the individual. At the heart of the concept of adaptation is adaptation to living systems and the external environment, and adaptation is both a process and the result of that process. In it, the concept of maladaptation reflects the mismatch of different degrees and qualities of organisms and environments. We all know that while full identity has an impact on development, full nonconformity is the opposite of the flow of life. In the same way, the term adaptation and maladaptation is applied to systems that occupy a place between these two poles; the first of them, adds compensatory and adaptive components, and the second, describes the system from the deficient and disruptive side.

List of used literature:

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA TABIATSHUNOSLIK FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNOLOGIYASI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada boshlang'ich sinflarda tabiatshunoslik fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalardan foydalanish bo'yicha ilmiy-pedagogik va metodik adabiyotlarni tahlil qilingan, fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarni mazmun-mohiyatini aniqlangan va ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tadqiqot maqsadi, tadqiqot vazifalari, ilmiy yangiligi, tavsiya ilmiy-pedagogik, metodik adabiyotlar, o'rganish va tahlil qilish, mazmun-mohiyati, metodik jihatlari, samaradorlig, ilmiy-metodik shakl, metod, vosita, qiyosiy tahlil, pedagogik tajriba, pedagogik kuzatuv, suhbat, test, tahlil, atrofimizdagi olam, interfaol metod, multimedia.

Аннотация. В статье проанализирована научно-педагогическая и методическая литература по использованию современных информационных технологий в обучении естествознанию в начальных классах, определены содержание и значение современных информационных технологий.

Ключевые слова. Цель исследования, задачи исследования, научная новизна, начальный класс, естествознание, современность, информационные технологии, научно-педагогическая рекомендация, методическая литература, изучение и анализ, содержание-сущность, интерактивный метод, мультимедиа.

Annotation. The article analyzes the scientific, pedagogical and methodological literature on the use of modern information technologies in teaching science in primary grades, determines the content and significance of modern information technologies in teaching natural science, the use of modern information technologies in teaching natural scienc.

Keywords. The purpose of the study, research objectives, scientific novelty, elementary grade, natural science, modernity, information technology, scientific and pedagogical recommendation, methodological literature, study and analysis, content-essence, methodological aspects, effectiveness, scientific and methodological form, method, tool.

Respublikamiz ta'lim muassasalarida intellektual rivojlangan shaxsni kamol toptirishning moddiy-texnik bazasi yaratildi, huquqiy-me'yoriy hujjatlar ishlab chiqildi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 28-yanvardagi "2022–2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi PF–60-son Farmonida 2026-yilga qadar o'quv dasturlari va darsliklarni ilg'or xorijiy tajriba asosida to'la qayta ko'rib chiqib, amalda joriy etish, maktablarda ta'lim sifatini oshirish, pedagog-kadrlarning bilimi va malakasini xalqaro darajaga olib chiqish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratgan³³.

Bu esa o'quvchilarda adabiy tushunchalarini shakllantirish orqali adabiy ta'limda yuksak samaradorlikka erishishga zamin yaratadi.

Axborot texnologiyalardan foydalanilganda ta'limda shaxsga-yo'naltirilgan yondashuvni amalga oshirish oson bo'lib qoldi, butun o'quv jarayonini samarali tashkil qilish imkoniyati paydo bo'ldi. Dars jarayonida tayyor multimediali mahsulotlari va kompyuter ta'limi dasturlaridan, o'quv va sinfdan tashqari ishlarda Internet tarmog'i vositalaridan foydalanib, multimediali ta'lim dasturlari va taqdimotlar, loyihalar yaratildi. Darslarda o'quvva o'yin dasturlaridan foydalanish katta samara beradi. Axborot texnologiyalarini barcha o'quv fanlarda qo'llash mumkin. "Tabiatshunoslik" fani bo'yicha "O'lkamiz suv havzalari", "Ona zamin", "O'rmon va dalalar — tabiat boyligi", "Qishloq xo'jaligi sohalari", "Bizning o'lka", "Yer osti boyliklari", "O'lkamiz hududiy tuzilishi", "O'lka chorvachiligi va o'simliklari" kabi

³³ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 28-январдаги "2022–2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг таракқиёт стратегияси тўғрисида"ги ПФ–60-сон Фармони. <https://lex.uz/pdfs/5841063>